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1 Project Overview

1.1 The ECO2 project

Energy Conscious Consumers (ECO2) is a project funded by Horizon 2020, the EU Research & Innovation Programme with nearly € 80 billion of funding allocated over a period of 7 years (2014-2020).

ECO2 will facilitate a large number of consumers to become conscious about and improve their energy efficiency. It will offer them two forms of learning: either they choose to go alone through an online e-learning platform, or they choose to be brought through transformative group learning, in which the e-learning system supports the group processes. Together the two – single or group processes – provide attractive approaches for a wide array of consumers segments. The ECO2 processes are based on “**blended**” engagement methods, making use of both online and dialogue elements.

Consumers will be recruited through different channels: social media, consumer media, energy suppliers and other gatekeepers. Segmentation will be used to increase the effectiveness of recruitment and to adapt the e-learning processes. The processes will be thematic, facilitated by an online ECO2 Platform, based on the online/blended engagement platform EngageSuite. Each consumer will be stepping up a “ladder of change” from **Motivation** to **Exploration** and finally to **Action**. In the process the user receives information, reflects/deliberates and seeks knowledge and knowledge sharing. The user creates his/her own action plan on the next personal steps to take. ECO2 will deliver “Actions” on five important themes:

- 1) **Change the house:** improving the footprint of the house and its appliances
 - 2) **Smart consumers:** make use of and understand ICT energy equipment
 - 3) **My Energy consumption:** understand energy language and bills
 - 4) **No rebound:** avoid making new energy consuming habits
 - 5) **Make your energy:** producing your own energy
-

Furthermore, an Action on co-creation of policies, innovations and designs will be executed and the results communicated to policy-makers and innovators through policy seminars. ECO2 has three phases:

- **Ramp-up:** makes the platform, segmentation analysis, story-boards and production of themes.
- **Pilot:** tests the Actions with voluntary consumers.
- **Up-scaling:** involves viral recruitment of consumers, expansion to new countries, and collaboration with consumers' gate-keepers.

ECO2 will continue after end of project by thanks to an established ECO2 Community and stakeholder responsibility for the ECO2 Platform.

1.2 List of Participants

The project brings together 9 partners from 9 different countries:

LIST OF PARTICIPANTS		
N°	PARTICIPANT LEGAL NAME	COUNTRY
1	FONDEN TEKNOLOGIRADET	Denmark
2	HEBES INTELLIGENCE Single Member P.C.	Greece
3	Sinergie Soc. Cons. a r.l.	Italy
4	HELSINGIN YLIOPISTO	Finland
5	DECO – ASSOCIACAO PORTUGUESA PARA ADEFESA DO CONSUMIDOR	Portugal
6	APPLIED RESEARCH AND COMMUNICATIONS FUND	Bulgaria
7	STRATEGIC DESIGN SCENARIOS SPRL	Belgium
8	ASSOCIACIJA ZINIU EKONOMIXOS FORUMAS	Lithuania
9	University College Cork	Ireland

2 ECO2 Storytelling concept

2.1 ECO2 Characters and their world

ECO2 will adopt an approach based on storytelling to present both project information, results and the platform contents.

The storytelling approach benefits the project as:

- It motivates users to explore deeply the platform;
- It provokes curiosity, hence it will increase the visualisation of ECO2 official communication channels and the visibility of the platform;
- It allows to present contents in a lighter and easy-to-comprehend way;
- It will help in defining the visual identity of the project as a whole and its dissemination/communication actions (i.e. it will be possible to use stories to communicate results, achievements, etc).

ECO2 has its own 'world', which is inhabited by characters, each with its own psychology, beliefs and behaviours.

The world in which ECO2 characters live is named Energyville, a city-state with its own laws, energy system and currency (the ECOs). The ECO currency could be used to make comparison among interventions/materials and as a possible indicator for economic savings. In this way the platform is free from different currencies existing in the EU.

The characters are:

- **Consumino**: the main character. Consumino guides users through the platform. He made lots of mistakes in configuring his house in the past and he shows how the issues have been solved.
- **Consumina**: the main character's twin sister. Consumina is also a main character. The episodes follow individual stories of both the male and the female main characters.

Consumino/a - gets easily angry, scared, worried, excited, is very lazy, and doesn't want to make an effort: "No, it's too complicated, I give up". (inspiration Donald Duck).

In the stories it appears either Consumino or Consumina. This is done in order to avoid to give preference to a gender assigning the role of main character.

- **Lampadino**: Consumino's dog making absurd comments. (inspiration Calvin and Hobbes)
 - **Led**: the kid is the inquisitive one, exposes the gap between what Consumino/a says and what he and she actually does, envious.
 - **Prosumina**: the nerd friend of Consumino. Prosumina always knows the best solution and lives in a highly energy-efficient technological house -> She often scolds Consumino for inefficient
-

behaviours. "Don't be such a cry baby, it's actually very simple." "I know for a fact that..." (inspiration Hermine)

- **Bill**: the evil character. He aims to take advantages from other characters' mistakes asking them money.

- **Billie Jean**: Bill's wife.

Bill and Billie drive a huge car, smoke cigars, always choose the cheapest investment, the quickest fix. Suggesting the wrong choice.

- **Granma Sòl**: Consumino's granma. She often says how people used to do things in old days. (Note: this character could be useful to introduce some theme to elderly people). GM has lived a long life, and is not prone to change. "That never killed me."

The **worker** points out - you need to buy a new freezer.

The **advisor** - knows about subsidies etc.

2.2 How to use stories to present actions' contents and objectives

Short stories will be told at the beginning of each action to introduce its objectives and the contents that will be showed to users. Stories can be told through short animated videos, strips or simply images on the screen with a narrative text. Strips and videos will be used at the beginning of the action as introduction and at its end, to wrap up conclusion and show a conclusion for the short story.

Below is an example on how to use story to introduce and close an action related to the purchase/change of a wood stove.

Story concept

Consumino and Prosumina are guests at Granma Sòl country house. It's winter and Granma Sòl is heating her home with an old wood stove. The stove is oversized and not very efficient (it is obsolete). The temperature inside is too high and Consumino's and Prosumina's eyes soon become irritated ... it is a possible clue that the stove could harm Granma's health. Consumino and Prosumina, at the table, when waiting for Granma (she's in the kitchen cooking the lunch) discuss on the possibility to buy her a new wood stove as a present. What is the best solution for Granma? What is the best size and the characteristics that it should have?

Screen 1 contents

Screen 1 will show a narrative text introducing the story and a short video developing it.

*“In this *episode* you will learn with Consumino what information should be kept in mind when purchasing a wood stove. Wood stoves could help you in saving money and could be a very efficient solution if chosen and configured correctly. If not, they could decrease your home comfort or, in the worst case, harm your health. [...]”*

At the end of the video a menu appears: users can choose what issue to analyse first. Each issue correspond to a different slide, in this way users can navigate the action.

Subsequent screens with technical contents

Subsequent screens contain images to show how the story continues (e.g. Prosumina explaining to Consumino the differences between existing wood stoves or Consumino going to purchase a wood stove and asking the seller to explain the energy label).

Apart of images advancing the story, technical screens contain different components such as navigable texts, technical videos or simulators.

Interaction is ensured through a short quiz, integrated with the story and the contents of the action.

Conclusion screen

The last screen should show a conclusion for the story showing what Consumino and Prosumina have chosen for Granma Sòl’s house. Then a ‘Call for action’ will follow to motivate users to make changes in their houses.

This example is inserted in Annex I in a storyboard template.

3 Definition of actions' storyboards

Storyboards are the blueprint for the actions to be developed as they contain all the details about contents, multimedia, interactions and assessments.

The ECO2 storyboards are intended as a flowchart illustrating the interaction between the different components with the objective to accompany users to achieve their goals.

Preliminary definitions:

- Dashboard: list of components that can be used to design contents.
- Components: media contents to be used in the action screens.
- Contents: information, stories, data and materials included in each screen with the aim to allow users to learn and take decisions about a specific topic (namely the ECO2 actions and sub-actions).
- Interaction and navigation: path conducting users from motivation to actions addressed to achieve their goals.
- Simulator: external app providing results and calculations starting from users' inputs.

The actions will be structured following the approach of transformative learning.

Transformative learning refers to those learning experiences that cause a shift in an individual's perspective. It is based on the idea that learning is "the process of making a new or revised interpretation of the meaning of an experience" (Mezirow, 1990). This happens when adult learners change their assumptions or expectations. What often follows is a change in their frame of reference for interpretation and understanding. The ways to foster transformative learning are:

- Relationships. Transformative learning is fostered by establishing supportive and trusting relationships. Building relationships requires a learning climate that is open to different perspectives and is non-hierarchical in nature. Online, trusting relationships are easier to build in virtual classroom or work group situations when participants can see each other through photos or video, when learners can hear the voice of the moderator or instructor and when they share a common goal.
 - Critical Reflection. Transformative learning often goes hand in hand with self-reflection. This involves challenging the assumptions people rely on to understand the world. For example, it is possible to foster transformative learning by asking open-ended questions that help learners relate new knowledge to their own life experiences. Probing questions that promote critical reflection have no easy or simple answer. It is possible to design critical reflection into formal courses by asking participants to respond to questions through blogging and other internal social tools. It can also be part of thoughtful online discussions.
-

- **Direct and Active Experience.** In his research review, Taylor (2007) found that one of the most powerful ways to foster transformative learning is by offering direct experiences that are meaningful to learners. This idea can be transferred to workplace learning by initiating programs that encourage direct experience. For example, doctors and nurses studying palliative care were required to visit hospices, funeral homes and anatomy labs.
- **Readiness for the Transformative Experience.** Another factor that encourages transformative learning is the individual's self-awareness and readiness for the experience. Individuals who are in a transitional mind-set are likely to experience a transformation. They may have been in the midst of a dilemma or at the limits of their ability to create meaning with their current level of knowledge. The implication is that it is important to help learners develop the type of self-awareness and acceptance of discomfort in order to allow a transformation to occur.
- **Discourse.** In her research review, Henderson (2010) points out how discussion is a critical aspect of transformative learning and that there are benefits to doing this online. First, some adults are more comfortable speaking online than in person, so they will be more engaged. Also, online discussions are flexible in mode. They may take place asynchronously in forums, so participants have time to think through their responses or they may take place synchronously in chat rooms. In addition, online discussions occur naturally when small groups tackle problems and issues.

The transformative learning process, then, begins when the learner carries out a conscious recognition of the differences between his old point of view and the new one provided through the learning process and decides it has more validity than the one in use. Therefore, transformative learning is realised when the learner is led to reflect on something that was taken for granted and that, if it was no more valid, would change his/her points of view.

4 The consumer's whole journey

The first step in designing the ECO2 platform is to understand who are its users and what are their goals in terms of learning and achievements.

Understanding users' needs will guide ECO2 team through the selection of media to be used and in designing the learning paths.

The ECO2 user is an EU citizen, exposed to energy issues, most likely aged 18+, with basic digital skills (i.e. able to use and interact with web 2.0 technologies). The aim is to involve users with different levels of energy literacy, focusing mainly on those having a low level of awareness. Users should be profiled when accessing the platform for the first time in order to allow them to follow a learning path in accordance with their level of skills and interests. For those having a low level of awareness and competence on energy issues, the ECO2 platform itself will constitute a tool to achieve a basic energy literacy.

According to the “Office of energy efficiency & renewable energy” of the US government, an energy-literate person¹:

- Can trace energy flows and think in terms of energy systems.
- Knows how much energy they use, for what purpose, and where the energy comes from.
- Can assess the credibility of information about energy.
- Can communicate about energy and energy use in meaningful ways.
- Is able to make informed energy-use decisions based on understanding of impacts and consequences.

The goal, therefore is to create a learning environment in which users can acquire energy-related basic skills, whenever not already held, and then become effective conscious consumers and informed decision-makers in realising their energy efficiency interventions. Therefore, users should be profiled and oriented through actions according to their level of expertise, classified from Basic (i.e. actions oriented to achieve energy literacy) to Advanced (i.e. actions oriented to become an expert energy consumer or a prosumer).

In selecting the actions, users will have the following options:

¹ <https://www.energy.gov/eere/education/energy-literacy-essential-principles-and-fundamental-concepts-energy-education>

- Go Alone: explore actions' contents individually.
- Join a group: users can explore actions within a group within which to share achievements, experiences and learning.

Contents will remain the same. In the case of group sessions, users will have the opportunity to interact with peers and mutually learn.

4.1 Archetypes of users (Personas) and scenarios

Personas are fictional but believable archetypes developed to represent ECO2 users. They go deeper than generalized customer segments by having individual names and stories that reflect personal attributes and behavioural characteristics such as needs, motivations, attitudes, and pain points

Maria the housewife

Maria is a 50 y.o. housewife. She is married and lives with her husband in a big European city. Maria takes care of the house and keeps track of expenses, including energy bills. She spends a lot of spare time using social media like Facebook. Her energy literacy level is low, but she is basically competent to use digital technologies according to her needs. She can navigate the internet and use Facebook and Youtube. ECO2 represents for her an opportunity to collect useful tips and learn what she can do in her daily life to save energy. She is attracted by the necessity to learn how to read her energy bill and how to save money. Through the platform she gains basic skills on basic energy literacy.

Carlo the engineer

Carlo is 40. He is a precise and meticulous industrial engineer. He often participates in continuing education courses, as well as he looks for technological articles or e-courses on the internet, to be always up-to-date with technological trends. ECO2 represents for him an opportunity to learn something new that can be useful both for his work and to make his home more energy efficient. Advanced topics on energy are the most interesting to Carlo, especially those addressed to prosuming.

Lambert the skilled worker

Lambert is 38 y.o. and is very pragmatic. He uses the internet to collect useful information, immediately applicable to improve his life. He looks for information on specific interventions at the moment once the need for such interventions manifests. He knows what he needs and just looks for "how-to-do it" contents which further explain what kind of resources are needed (professionals, building materials, electronic devices, etc.). He is able to analyse the costs and benefit of actions – especially those that he can partially or totally do alone. Lambert is more prone to enroll to intermediate and advanced actions.

Mirka the young student

Mirka is 14 y.o. and is a curious girl. She participates in extra-curricular activities proposed by her school. Among them, she is attracted by the ECO2 group activities which propose games and simulation activities on how to protect the environment through common actions and behaviours

that can be adopted at home. She is enthusiast about this learning and, when at home, transfers the knowledge (she has gained through the ECO2 platform) to her family and invites them to use the ECO2 platform to learn more.

Ornella the environmentalist

Ornella is 28. She is an activist in environmental associations. She is passionate about trekking and other outdoor activities and, when is not adventuring in the nature, she reads a lot of books and web-articles on environmental topics. She is interested in finding new battles to fight. Sometimes she enrolls in MOOCs² on the same topics. ECO2 represents for her an opportunity to learn what she can do to reduce environmental impacts of one of the most impacting human activity, namely the energy consumption of the residential sector. She is interested to learn more. At the end of her actions, she can become a multiplier of ECO2 promotion activities as well as be interested in becoming a facilitator of ECO2 action groups.

Alima the university student

Alima is a 21 y.o. student of engineering. She is curious and has advanced digital skills. She always searches MOOCs on STEM³ disciplines to deepen her knowledge and competences, especially in subject not included in her university curriculum. ECO2 is a good opportunity to learn something new, with the added value to teach her actions she can do to save energy at her home. Alima could become a facilitator in a group of peers.

Horatio the retired

Horatio is 74, is retired since 4 years. He's very attentive in money saving and when he receives a very high bill he start to collect information through the local customer association and through the internet (he has basic skills related to use search engines and social medias). He learns about the existence of local ECO2 action groups and he decides to join one. The group help him to achieve basic energy literacy and train him on how to use the platform to learn more. Horatio is enthusiast of this new learning and transfer it to his sons, promoting the use of the ECO2 platform.

²Massive open online courses

³ Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Maria, housewife, 50 y.o., married
 - attentive to money saving;
 - high use of social media;
 - basic digital literacy;
 - low energy literacy;
 - taking care of the house and therefore knows very well its needs

Sequence	Anticipation	Research	Consideration	Application	Reflect				
Call to action	Maria receives a high energy bill or an appliance suddenly breaks		Find ECO2 (well indicised) on Facebook and Google	Contents presented in a light way; Attractive materials and stories; Gamification and being part of a community	Learn and solve the problem (in this case collect needed information to save money on her bill or gain knowledge to consciously buy an appliance)				
Action	Start collecting information with neighbours, friends, relatives and through the internet	Maria searches on Google (and maybe Youtube will be the first results) and on her social media channels (mainly Facebook or Instagram)	Click and read what is ECO2	Start using the platform and maybe join a ECO2 group (virtual or physical)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can take actions responsive to her needs - learn and take decisions - provide feedbacks on her decisions - obtain a score/reward in her ECO2 profile - can share the achievement in her social media 				
Touchpoints		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facebook - Youtube - Google 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECO 2 Facebook page - ECO 2 Youtube videos - ECO 2 website - ECO 2 Platform 	ECO2 platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECO 2 Platform - Maria's social media channels 				
Positive			3 Maria finds ECO2	4 Interest/curiosity attracted	5 Registration and log-in	6 Profiling	7 Takes responsive actions	8 Learns and takes decisions	9 provides feedbacks and shares achievements
Neutral		2 Search in internet and social medias							
Negative	1 Maria needs information								
Moment of truth			ECO2 should be indicised	Contents should reflect her needs and be appropriate for her skills	Maria takes decisions and provides feedback to the ECO2 platform. If satisfied, she shares the achievement in her social media accounts attracting other users with a similar profile.				

<p>Carlo, Engineer, 40 y.o. Meticulous Looks for specific and very technical information Could be interested in telling his point of view and 'teach' something to other users May interact with the platform staff and community</p>					
Sequence	Anticipation	Research	Consideration	Application	Reflect
Call to action	Carlo should be constantly updated on new technologies and professional methodologies	Carlo is interested to know about new technologies for energy saving	Carlo finds ECO2 well indicised and finds banner and ads that attract his attention	Contents presented with a high level of specificity; very advanced topics	Carlo learns new things and takes advanced actions for his home (or proposes them to his customers). Carlo finds the opportunity to be a facilitator of ECO2 groups - this could help him with visibility and attracting new clients
Action	Carlo consults sectorial magazines, technical blogs and on google		Carlo reads all information and clicks the banners to go to ECO2 official channels	Carlo decides to enroll and explore ECO2 options	Carlo takes actions, participates in a group and is attracted by the opportunity to become a facilitator
Touchpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Google (Google ads) - Advertising in sectorial magazines - Banner in technical blogs/portals - ads on Social Media 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECO 2 facebook, Google+, Youtube, Twitter - ECO 2 LinkedIn group - ECO 2 website 	ECO2 platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECO 2 platform - ECO 2 local group
Positive					
Neutral					
Negative					
Moment of truth	Attractive promotion		Presentation of the ECO2 platform objectives and opportunities	Satisfaction with materials and concrete achievements	

<p>Mirka, student 14 y.o. - Curious girl - loves teaching her parents what she learns at school - does a lot of extra-curricular activities</p>					
Sequence	Anticipation	Research	Consideration	Application	Reflect
Call to action	Mirka's school launches a workshop on energy and environmental issues as extra curricular activities		Mirka enrolls in the extra curricular activity	Mirka and other students simulate actions related to energy saving, conservation/creation at home	Mirka and her peers learn and act as multipliers to their families. The students cannot enroll directly to the platform but can show it to their families and convince them in creating an account. Some simple behaviours can be adopted directly by students at home (e.g. turn off the videogames instead to leave them in stand-by).
Action	Mirka searches for information on the workshop objectives: what she can learn and what is the purpose of the activities		Mirka takes part in the working group and participates in discussion	The students make experiments and learn useful skills and knowledge. Part of the action is related on how to transfer all these learnings to their families. Platform is used as a support for the group session.	Students transfer what they learn to their families and take simple actions at home.
Touchpoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - School's website and social media - School bulletin board - Mirka's teachers involved in the workshop 		ECO2 physical group session at school	ECO2 physical group session at school and ECO2 platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ECO2 platform, social media and communication materials - Informative and training materials used by Mirka and other students at the ECO2 school group
Positive	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between; align-items: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 18%;">1 Mirka loves science and tech and is excited to participate to a workshop on energy and environmental issues</div> <div style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">→</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 18%;">2 Mirka enrolls and starts the group activities such as experiments, simulations, experiential learning</div> <div style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">→</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 18%;">3 Mirka learns about the importance of energy saving at home. Some possible actions to teach to adult family members are taught.</div> <div style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">→</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 18%;">4 The facilitators show the ECO2 tools that families could use to learn more</div> <div style="width: 10%; text-align: center;">→</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; width: 18%;">5 Mirka learns what she can do to help her family to save energy and money. She is enthusiast on what she learnt and transfers that to her family. ECO2 platform is also presented</div> </div>				
Neutral					
Negative					
Moment of truth	Objectives and structure made interesting for high-school students		Group activities are exciting	New ECO2 accounts created	

	<p>Ornella, 28 y.o. - Ecologist, attentive to environmental issues - Discusses with people with different thinking - activist in environmentalist organisations</p>				
<p>Sequence</p>	<p>Anticipation</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Consideration</p>	<p>Application</p>	<p>Reflect</p>
<p>Call to action</p>	<p>Ornella is curious on environmental themes and spends a lot of her spare time in looking for information and articles on the web.</p>	<p>Ornella start blaming residential building consumption as part of the problem on climate change. She starts thinking that her new mission is to become an 'evangelist' of energy saving.</p>	<p>She learns that through the ECO2 actions she could learn what it is possible to do to save energy, beginning from her home</p>	<p>She is attracted by content and expected results of each action in terms of impacts and reductions</p>	<p>Ornella learns and adopts efficient behaviour at home. She believes that she can transfer the knowledge to her friends and relatives.</p>
<p>Action</p>	<p>She looks for new battles to fight</p>	<p>A call to action is inside ECO2 posts on social media and web articles, explaining the environmental impacts of residential buildings</p>	<p>Visiting the platform, Ornella chooses the best actions she can implement.</p>	<p>Ornella enrolls in the platform and starts individual and group sessions</p>	<p>She also learns about the opportunity to become a facilitator of ECO2 groups and starts the related training. In this way she maximises the impact of participating to the ECO2 actions</p>
<p>Touchpoints</p>	<p>ECO2 web articles and social media posts</p>		<p>ECO2 platform</p>	<p>ECO2 platform</p>	<p>ECO2 platform; social media</p>
<p>Positive</p>					
<p>Neutral</p>					
<p>Negative</p>					
<p>Moment of truth</p>	<p>Attractive article</p>		<p>Environmental impacts are part of the foreseen impact of the action</p>	<p>Ornella gains valuable knowledge; apply it at home and becomes a facilitator</p>	

	<p>Alima, 21 y.o. Student - Alima studies Civil Engineering at the University of Amsterdam - She is very curious on technological and scientific themes and takes any opportunity offered to learn new things (she is enrolled in lot of MOOCs related to STEM) - She is a digital native</p>				
<p>Sequence</p>	<p>Anticipation</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Consideration</p>	<p>Application</p>	<p>Reflect</p>
<p>Call to action</p>	<p>Alima always needs new ideas and is attracted by science.</p>	<p>Alima looks for MOOCs and other learning opportunities to deepen the knowledge acquired at the university or to learn on new topics</p>	<p>Interesting action/learning session found on the ECO2 platform</p>		<p>Alima is satisfied with what she learnt. Next step is to transfer her new knowledge to her peers and relatives. The opportunity to be a facilitator of a group of peers is exposed</p>
<p>Action</p>	<p>She always looks for opportunity to learn something new</p>	<p>ECO2 is presented as a stimulating learning opportunity on energy topics</p>	<p>Alima finds ECO2 platform and starts exploring contents and learning objectives</p>	<p>Alima enrolls and starts learning</p>	<p>Alima concludes B+I+A actions and shares her results. Some simple actions could be adopted at home (especially those related to the change of behaviour). Alima shares her achievement and promotes the platform. She becomes the facilitator of a group of peers</p>
<p>Touchpoints</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Google - Social Media - Google Ads - Facebook ads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Google - Social Media - Google Ads - Web articles 	<p>ECO2 platform</p>	<p>ECO2 platform</p>	<p>ECO2 platform and Alima' social media</p>
<p>Positive</p>					
<p>Neutral</p>					
<p>Negative</p>					
<p>Moment of truth</p>	<p>Good contents on ECO2 platform and good presentation of the learning objectives</p>				<p>Alima satisfaction and expectations reached</p>

	<p>Horatio, 74 years old, retired</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - finds it difficult to use web-based technologies (he logs on facebook, check emails) - interested in better understanding why he has to pay energy (he cannot read the energy bill) - Very active in participating in a discussion group 				
<p>Sequence</p>	<p>Anticipation</p>	<p>Research</p>	<p>Consideration</p>	<p>Application</p>	<p>Reflect</p>
<p>Call to action</p>	<p>Horatio complains about his energy bills</p>	<p>The customer association employee gives him promotional materials on ECO2 platform and the local discussion group</p>	<p>Horatio participates in the discussion group where the platform is presented. The group teaches how to read the energy bill and simulates participants how to save energy (ECO2 platform is used as a supporting tool)</p>	<p>Horatio is satisfied and wants to learn more. He wants to deepen his activity through the ECO2 platform</p>	<p>Horatio is very happy on the achievements related to the group action he took, so he wants to share his experience with his sons. He also needs their help to use the ECO2 platform</p>
<p>Action</p>	<p>He goes to customer associations and googles to find answers to his problems</p>	<p>Horatio takes the opportunity to go to a discussion where he expects to find a group complaining on same issues</p>	<p>Horatio discusses, reports his experience and starts learning through simulations and games</p>	<p>Horatio reach the platform. He finds difficult to register, so he asks for help.</p>	<p>Horatio shows the platform ato his sons. His sons helps him to register and learn about the existence of ECO2 actions. Their sons could become new users.</p>
<p>Touchpoints</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Customer association - Google 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Customer association - Google 	<p>Local discussion group</p>	<p>ECO2 Platform</p>	<p>ECO2 platform</p>
<p>Positive</p>					
<p>Neutral</p>					
<p>Negative</p>					
<p>Moment of truth</p>		<p>Engaging and interesting activities at ECO2 groups</p>		<p>Usability of the platform</p>	<p>Achievements</p>

5 The building blocks of the storyboards

In the context of ECO2, storyboards are scenarios or scripts that describe the way a user may go through and interact with the contents of the platform. While different storyboards correspond to different scenarios of user-platform interactions, all storyboards will utilise the same set of building blocks.

5.1 “Match challenges to content” block

This block lists the different challenges that users may face and for which the ECO2 content is able to provide guidance. It can be implemented as a searchable set of problems/issues or as a simple chat-bot that interacts with users by associating their problems and questions with challenges addressed by ECO2. In either case, it directs users to the relevant content.

5.2 “ECO2 mascots have the same challenges too” block

This block aims at helping users associate their challenges with content that exists on the ECO2 platform. It is structured around stories of fictitious characters (ECO2 mascots) facing similar challenges and asking similar questions as the users. It presents the options that are available to the mascots (and the users) for improving the energy efficiency or sufficiency of their houses. The stories will showcase the problems, the options employed, the results, and what the results tell us about the root causes of the problems.

5.3 “Quiz” block

Quizzes can challenge common beliefs and misconceptions, as well as fuel interest and direct users' to different sections of the content. For example:

5.4 “No-variation content” block

This block represents one or more pages that include content that is valid without relying on strong assumptions. Each page is any combination of text, images, videos, and links to external sources of credible, relevant information.

5.5 “Multiple-variations content” block

A central strategy of content development is that content should be customizable (to users’ conditions). The less assumptions and generalisations we include into the content, the more useful it will be. Accordingly, wherever possible, multiple variations of the same content will be developed. Multiple variations of the same content will be accessible to users through:

- “Data collection” blocks
- “Impact comparison across options” blocks
- “Impact comparison across conditions” blocks

5.6 “Data collection” block

This block allows users to enter data that reflect their particular conditions (regarding the building envelope, HVAC and other equipment, energy consumption, weather conditions, etc.). Different data is requested at different places in the content, but all data is associated with each user’s profile. After entering their data, users are directed to the content version that is most relevant for them (note that there will be a small number of variations for each piece of content, so user conditions and content assumptions will never match perfectly).

5.7 “Impact comparison across options” block

This block allows users to compare the impact and value of different technology options or efficiency interventions under similar conditions. Users can choose an option and see the results,

an explanation regarding why this impact was achieved, and how option compares to the alternatives. Users can go back to the option selection menu and choose another option or access a summary table that compares different options side by side.

5.8 “Impact comparison across conditions” block

This block allows users to compare the impact and value of one technology option or efficiency intervention under different conditions. Its main goal is to present what drives the economic value of different interventions through a series of boundary examples.

5.9 “How it works” block

This block aims to explain the basic concepts that define the rationale and expected impact of the energy efficiency actions promoted by ECO2. This block is composed of one or more pages combining:

- text;
- simple diagrams that summarise the message of each page; and
- plots that embody quantitative aspects (so that to avoid including numbers in the text).

Alternatively, the text can be narrated by each ECO2 partner in their own language.

5.10 “Input-output model” block

This block includes interactive models that are defined by the aspects that a user is allowed to experiment with (inputs) and the results that the user is presented with (visualised outputs). As an example, for the case of sizing and identifying the most important parameters of a wood stove, an input-output model could include:

1. Inputs: Room size, wall insulation (very good, average to good, poor or non-existent), air tightness, outdoor weather conditions (e.g. min and max daily temperature), efficiency of the wood stove, size of the wood stove.
2. Outputs: The relation between the mean radiant temperature (a good indicator for thermal comfort) and the required fuel supply (in terms of both amount of wood logs and cost), as well as the refuelling rate that is required for different levels of radiant temperature .

These models are interactive dashboards embedded in the ECO2 platform. As a result, they require additional context from the platform that will guide users to experiment with the model, uncover cause-effect relationships, and derive insights on their own.

5.11 “User feedback” block

This block aims at allowing users to give feedback to the ECO2 team either by answering to surveys or by providing small text (limited number of characters) with ideas, concerns, wishes etc.

Feedbacks from users are collected:

- Through a questionnaire/survey appearing at their first access to be used to profile them and to suggest them a tailored learning path;
- Through the creation of a user profile in which achievements at the end of actions are automatically recorded. The inspiration for users’ profiles could be taken from Ps4 (Playstation 4) trophies:

The role of user profiles is to motivate users to make achievements, to share them with others, and as well to allow the ECO2 consortium to keep track of users actions and their impacts.

5.12 ECO2 story line elements: use of models in the platform (elements number E and results calculation R)

The e-learning storylines would sometimes need calculations/models to show/teach logics in energy saving and/or to react on input from the user. We have identified five ways of integrating models in the platform:

E1: Simulation

An infographic shows a device – for example a thermostat. Changing the input results in illustration of the consequence – for example of using the thermostat as a function of the wished in-house temperature, the outside temperature and the isolation standard of the house. The output can be shown as a graph or as below a performance, maybe compared to EU average energy usage per square meter house.

Technically this demands some coding for all elements, so the solution cannot be generic – it will have to be developed for each simulation we would wish to make. So, this should only be used when we really know there will be added value.

E2: Calculation of solution

A picture shows a simplified calculation problem – for example, which type of window should I buy? In connection are some simplified questions, e.g.:

Which inside temperature do you want? 21

Which type of climate do you live in (choose a city climate that is closest to yours)? Helsinki / London / Berlin / Paris / Rome

How well is your house isolated? Very well / Medium / Low isolation

Solution: You would get the best result with: 1 layer glass / 2 layer glass / 2 layer thermo / 2 layer thermo climate / **3 layer thermo climate glass**

Technically this is simple, because it needs a good illustration, standard survey questions, and a little coding, which makes use of the answers in the survey questions.

E3: Pre-calculated scenarios

One can imagine a model, which is very complicated, and which would demand sophisticated calculations – think of simulation of a national energy system, which often takes models using several minutes of calculations on a super-computer to generate the output.

We will not be able to integrate such models in the platform for technical reasons, including the lack of access to these sophisticated models. But what we could do would be to create a set of scenarios, based on a limited amount of choices, and show the results as pictures of scenario outputs.

So, we don't calculate anything – we show pictures according to the choices the user makes.

Technically this is trivial, but the pre-work in terms of making the right scenarios and making the pre-calculations could be demanding – but feasible.

E4: Choice of value-dependent solutions

Some of the options above may be added other choices/decisions than the technical ones. For example, the window-example above may be added a choice, such as:

*What would a main determinant for your choice of solution? Cheapest / **Most CO2 efficient** / Most comfortable / Easiest to install / Beautiful to look at / Other _____*

Such value-based questions could be added to model-based calculations to filter the results according to preferences.

E5: Compare scenarios

Based on the input from the user the above calculation methods can be used to present the user for comparison of solutions/scenarios: Now $\leftarrow \rightarrow$ Scen1 Scen1 $\leftarrow \rightarrow$ Scen2

This might especially be helpful for group processes, in which an ECO2 group can compare their individually preferred scenarios.

However, we will probably not be able to make “group results”, since such would take quite much adaption to the platform, which could hardly be made in a generic fashion. Therefore, comparison of scenarios would have to be based on several sets of scenario input from the single user. The fact that we will have single online users supports this solution.

R1: Input-based calculation of user performance and KPIs

A special calculation tool could be made to help giving the user feedback on performance and at the same time to make data for our project performance in terms of KPIs.

These could be made from a set of performance scores, depending on the input we get from the user:

- 1) “Validated results”: The user reports that an energy saving action has been done. This results in a 100% performance score, which can be calculated into kW and/or CO2 saved. This score is used for both the user performance (Green color / very happy Prosumina) and the project performance “Validated KPI”.
- 2) “Validated intention”: The user reports to want to make a behavior change, but did not report to have made the change. This would result in a 50% performance score (recalculated to Kw/CO2). This score goes to the user performance (Yellow-green color / Prosumina nearly happy), and it goes to a project “Shadow-KPI or not-validated KPI”.
- 3) “Validated exploration”: We can see that the user has used the Action, the models etc, but no intentions or change has been reported. This would result in a 25% performance for the user (Yellow color / Prosumina looks a little irritated), and for the Shadow project KPI.

These calculations would, thus, give three forms of performance indicators:

- a) The user's performance in the specific Action, which may sum up to an accumulated User Performance.
- b) The "Validated project KPI", based on reported change only, across all users.
- c) The "Shadow project KPI", based on reported + intended + exploration-based performance scores across all users.

Story-telling options connected to the use of models and calculations

- The Advisor would be important – could explain the model – could give hints on how to improve performance. With a little too technical or even arrogant attitude, sometimes: "This is difficult to calculate but I have been educated to do that, of course"
- Prosumina would also give advice, but with a normative twist: "Well done, and good for the climate as well".
- Bill may give comments when the outcome of the calculations pays off economically.
- Granma may wave the finger "and remember to report it when you have done it. And don't forget to actually do it!"

6 Structure of the different actions and interaction between the building blocks

6.1 Difficulty level of the different actions

As stated in chapter 4, actions may be classified according to their difficulty level and the depth of contents in three different levels:

Basic actions.

Basic actions' objective is to provide basic energy literacy to users. This will allow them to start learning simple tips on how to save energy and what they could do if they want to learn and do more. Basic actions will be addressed to users with a low level of knowledge on energy topics. They work as e-learning courses with specific "call to actions" at the end, reporting and sharing the results of the adopted actions. Basic actions are inserted in 'Change the house' and 'My energy consumption' actions.

Intermediate actions.

The objective of Intermediate actions is to transform common and 'passive' users into proactive and well informed users. Intermediate actions will include interventions that are more complex than those proposed in basic actions and that are not simply addressed to change users' behaviours. Basic actions can be directly translated into real interventions and changes in behaviour without relying on professionals such as plant installers, construction workers or other specialised technicians. Intermediate actions may require the interventions made by these professionals. Intermediate actions are included in 'Change the house', 'My energy consumption' and 'Smart consumer' actions.

Advanced actions.

Advanced actions aim to transform users to prosumers and to teach them possible advanced interventions they can realise at home, as well as advanced topics in energy technologies. Advanced actions require the intervention of a specialised professional or more than one professionals. Advance actions include advanced topics in the ‘Smart Consumer’ action and all topics of ‘Making my energy’ and ‘No rebound’.

6.2 Structure of individual actions (IA)

The “learn and decide” structure (IA1)

Motivation: screen presenting the action and the learning objectives, as well as the expected achievements.

Intro: story (video or comic strip) introducing the energy problem faced [“ECO2 mascots have the same challenges too” block].

Teaching screens: “No-variation content” block; “Multiple-variations content” block; “How it works” block.

QUIZ: “Quiz” block.

Users’ feedbacks: “Input-output model” block + User feedbacks block.

Decisions and KPI: report of achievements in the users’ profile and quantification of impact

The 'explore and decide' structure (IA2)

Teaching screen: It should specifically address a problem to be solved. The teaching screen should teach where and how to search for information.

Exploration: External web articles and technical resources. It would be necessary to create a function that allows users to highlight information they consider useful to solve the problem. Highlighted informations are automatically included in the 'Report main findings' screen.

Exploration: simulation and/or calculation tools that show how the problem can be solved according some input parameters and variables. Results (and the inserted parameters/variables) should be transferred automatically to the 'Report main findings' screen. This exploration screen could be created through multiple-variations content; Impact comparison across options; Impact comparison across conditions; Input-output model blocks.

Report main findings: a screen summarising the results from the exploration activities. The results may be posted and discussion on the forum before taking decisions.

Take decision: will be created as a 'Quiz' with open questions asking the users what they have decided to do and what is the foreseen/planned time.

Report the achievements: after some weeks/months the users should report the achievement and – if they want – provide/upload some pictures on the realised interventions. A reminder will be sent by the platform to invite users to do that and conclude the action.

The ‘now it’s time to do that’ structure (IA3)

User’s input: a specific problem related to an energy-related technology (e.g. appliances, insulation systems, cooler, heaters) or energy decision is presented to the user. The screen asks the user to insert data related to the user’s house. This screen is made with the data collection block.

Potential gain: the platform shows the potential gain specifically calculated on user inputs if they adopt the technology/decision.

Teaching screens: Screens that will teach what to do, the different steps to adopt the technology or take the decision.

Exploration screens: additional external sources and simulation tools

Report main findings: collect results from the exploration activities and a summary of the teaching screens.

Take decisions and report: decision is taken, the users will be asked to insert the achievements related to the action.

6.3 Structure of group actions (GA)

The 'let's see what happens' structure (GA1)

Intro: it contains learning objectives and expected achievements and a short video or article introducing a topic.

Input/output model: simulation tool. The approach of this action is related to 'learning by doing'

Call to action: invitation made by the facilitator to replicate at home the action learnt in the simulation and to report the achievements and results to the benefit of other users.

The first part (until the 'call to action' from the facilitator) could be done either online or offline through physical workshops. The reporting is done online, as well as the final feedback given by the facilitator.

The 'divide et impera' structure (GA2)

This structure represents a group session organised as a physical meeting, which concludes with a call to actions aimed to bring the participants to the ECO2 platform in order to share the results of the concluded action.

Intro: The facilitator presents the objectives of the day, the project and the ECO2 platform.

Case study and work in groups: some case studies are presented (e.g. a person who reduces the energy bill or a refurbished house). Then the facilitator assigns some topics to be discussed and on which the facilitator will collect inputs and feedback from the users. Users then break out in different small groups. Ideally, 1 group per topic should be set up. The facilitator assigns to 1 person at a table the role of the 'host'. The host does not change the group while other members rotate from one group to another every 30 minutes. The host has the responsibility to keep track of the discussions and to continue the discussion on the same topic when group members rotate. The host takes notes on the discussion through a white table papercloth and through post-its to collect the main findings.

Presentation of results of group: At the end of the discussions, the facilitator prepares a wall on which summaries of information from the tables and post-its will be exposed. Hosts will rotate to illustrate to all participants the results of the discussion they managed.

Creation of a mailing list and a virtual group: the facilitator then asks the participants if they want to deepen their learning on the group topics. For those accepting, the facilitator asks them for their e-mail addresses to send them the report of the day with the main findings.

Achievements from the day: the facilitator keeps record on the achievements and expected results from actions discussed by the groups. These will be included in project KPIs.

Call for action: the facilitator sends the report and a request for an action/intervention to be realised by the participants at home by a fixed deadline. Then the facilitator invites users to keep track of improvements and report in a specific section of the ECO2 platform (data collection block). The facilitator sends then feedback and validates the reports, allowing the results of the action to be recorded in users’ profiles and included in ECO2 KPIs.

The ‘Come, learn and spread the word’ structure (GA3)

This structure is perfect for a physical group session (e.g. in schools). During the 2 days of the workshop the participant will learn about energy saving and environmental protection issues. A small call for action is assigned and discussed on the second day. The results will be discussed and recorded. The main objective is to train the participants to ‘spread the word’ to their relatives and friends, transforming the participants into multipliers of the promotion activities of the ECO2 platform.

7 Conclusions and next steps

Different users will use the platform with different purposes. In the recruiting phase, it will be extremely important to diversify the contents of the communication, diversifying according the different needs expected for each users categories. It should be clearly stated that through the platform they will solve a problem. Basic actions (Energy literacy) as well should be oriented towards achieving this objective.

Regarding the creation of contents for each specific action, the first step will be – after having identified the goal of the action and defined the sub-actions - to select the most appropriate structure from the ones presented in this document. Then what is inside each block will follow. The table below summarises the suggested structure for the different ECO2 actions according to their difficulty level.

ECO2 actions	Change the house	My energy consumption	Smart Consumer	No rebound	Making my energy
Basic actions	IA1, GA1, GA2, GA3	IA1, GA1, GA2, GA3	/	/	/
Intermediate actions	IA2, GA1, GA2	IA2, GA1, GA2	IA1, IA2, GA1, GA2	/	/
Advanced actions	/	/	IA3, GA1, GA2	IA3, GA1, GA2	IA3, GA1, GA2

The storytelling approach will help in presenting contents in a lighter way and could be used in the promotional activities. Stories could be developed as example/case studies to be showed to users as well as promotion materials to attract new users to the ECO2 platform. Annex I contains an example on how to use the characters and their stories to present contents.

7.1 Revisions

The current document has been internally revised by ARC FUND and by external experts. The table below summarises their suggestions and comments.

Revision history

Name of the reviewer	Organisation	Date	Comments	Suggestions
Zoya Damianova	ARC FUND	30/07/2018	Minor corrections and formatting	Clarifications needed in some points
Giovanni Pede	SINERGIE	02/08/2018	Comments and questions by ARC FUND addressed.	/
Karen Riisgaard, Lucas Larsen	DBT	09/08/2018	Revision of text	
Zdravko Georgiev	SOFENA, Sofia Energy Agency	02-24/08/2018	Doubts on the path of Horatio through the platform	Substitute the first access of the platform with printed materials
Todor Galev	Center for the Study of Democracy			Modify step 6 of Horatio's path
Marko Hajdinjak	ARC FUND, ENERGISE project			Minor corrections and clarifications

Annex I

Title: Wood stoves for Granma Sòl

Screen: 1

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p><i>In this episode you will learn with Consumino what information should be kept in mind when purchasing a wood stove. Wood stoves could help you in saving money and could be a very efficient solution if chosen and configured correctly. If not, they could decrease your home comfort or, in the worst case, harm your health. Consumino and Prosumina discovered that after a lunch with Granma Sòl. Another energy problem. Will Consumino and Prosumina solve it?"</i></p>	<p>Visual description</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Video telling this story:</p> <p>Consumino and Prosumina are guests at Granma Sòl country house. It's winter and Granma Sòl is heating her home with an old wood stove. The stove is oversized and not very efficient. The temperature inside is too high and Consumino and Prosumina's eyes soon become irritated. There are also some smoke in the room, a clue that the combustion does not work well. There is the risk that the stove could harm Granma's health. Consumino and Prosumina, at the table, when waiting for Granma (she's in the kitchen cooking the lunch) discuss the possibility to buy her a new wood stove as a present. What is the best solution for Granma? What is the best size and the characteristics the wood stove should have?</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The objective of the current action - The problems related with the use of wood stoves for heating - The contents of the action
<p>Branching and interactions</p> <p>At the end of the video a menu appears: users can choose what issue to analyse first. Each issue correspond to a different slide, in this way users can navigate the action.</p>	

Title: **Wood stoves for Granma Sòl**

Screen: **2**

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p>Screen 2 gives a definition of wood stoves.</p> <p>A navigable technical text is included in the screen.</p>	<p>Visual description</p> <p>Navigable technical text [different kinds of wood stoves, fuel, etc]</p> <p>Click to external sources (embedded in the page)</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Image (comic) with Prosumina explaining to Consumino what a wood stove is.</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <p>Different kind of wood stoves and their pros and cons</p>
<p>Branching and interactions</p> <p>Clicking on keywords a box with explanation appears and/or a box with external sources/medias (videos, technical schemes etc.)</p>	

Title: **Wood stoves for Granma Sòl**

Screen: **3**

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p>Consumino and Prosumina continue the discussion.</p> <p>A calculator/simulator is embedded in the screen</p>	<p>Visual description</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Calculator</p> <p>Comic strip with the discussion</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <p>How to choose the right dimension</p>

Title: **Wood stoves for Granma Sòl**

Screen: **4**

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p>Some days later, Consumino goes to a store to see some wood stove. He asks to the seller how to read an energy label and how to use this information to choose.</p>	<p>Visual description</p> <p>Image representing a seller and a store</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Image representing the scene of Consumino at the wood stoves store.</p>	
<p>Branching and interactions</p> <p>Go to wood stoves explanation Go to 'sum up'</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <p>How to read energy label</p>

Title: **Wood stoves for Granma Sòl**

Screen: **5**

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p>Consumino goes to Prosumina’s house, they sum up what they have learnt and the characteristics to be taken into consideration to choose a wood stove</p>	<p>Visual description</p> <p>Hi Prosumina, we have to think what kind of stove we should buy to Granma</p> <p>OK, let's think about what we learnt..</p> <p>Navigable text</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Image representing Consumino at Prosumina’s house</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <p>Sum up of what they learn with previous screen</p>
<p>Branching and interactions</p> <p>Go back to previous screen</p> <p>Go to the quiz</p>	

Title: **Wood stoves for Granma Sòl**Screen: **6**

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p>Quiz</p> <p>Consumino and Prosumina give room size and needs of Granma Sol's house. The users should select the best choice</p> <p>Some other questions are asked to users</p>	<p>Visual description</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Interactive quiz</p>	
<p>Branching and interactions</p> <p>Go to conclusion (what Consumino and Prosumino choose)</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <p>Consideration to choose a wood stove</p>

Title: **Wood stoves for Granma Sòl**

Screen: **7**

<p>Narrative/Script</p> <p>Conclusion with the final choice of Consumino and Prosumina</p>	<p>Visual description</p>
<p>Audio/Music/SFX and other medias</p> <p>Video telling the conclusion of the story</p>	<p>What the user will learn</p> <p>Consideration to choose a wood stove</p>
<p>Branching and interactions</p> <p>Go to discussion Forum Go to main platform menu</p>	

